

The Performance of EDXS at Elevated Sample Temperatures Using a MEMS-Based *In Situ* TEM Heating System

Robert Krisper^{a,b,*}, Judith Lammer^{a,b}, Yevheniy Pivak^c, Evelin Fisslthaler^a, Werner Grogger^{a,b}

^a Graz Centre for Electron Microscopy (ZFE), Austrian Cooperative Research (ACR), Steyrergasse 17, 8010 Graz, Austria

^b Institute of Electron Microscopy and Nanoanalysis (FELMI), Graz University of Technology, Steyrergasse 17, 8010 Graz, Austria

^c DENSolutions, Informaticalaan 12, Delft, 2628ZD, The Netherlands

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

in situ TEM
in situ heating
 EDXS
 solid angle
 detector shadowing
 energy resolution

ABSTRACT

Since the development of MEMS heating holders, dynamic *in-situ* experiments at elevated temperatures may be complemented by X-ray spectrometry for chemical analysis. Although the amount of IR radiation is small when compared to furnace holders, the influence of IR radiation emitted from the heating device on the quality of the X-ray spectra is significant. In this work, we systematically examine the influence of infrared (IR) radiation generated by MEMS-based *in situ* heating systems (DENSolutions single- and double-tilt holders) on the results and interpretation of energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectra through simulation and measurement. Focal points of interest in this study are the influence of holder geometry, shadowing and orientation with respect to the different emission characteristics of IR and X-ray photons and their interaction with a side-entry and a multi-detector system. IR photons substantially contribute to count rates, dead time, electronic noise levels, energy resolution, and detection efficiency of semiconductor detectors. At higher sample temperatures, they ultimately limit the feasibility of EDXS for elemental characterization and especially the traceability of low-Z elements. This work provides a quantitative insight into the influence of all relevant parameters related to *in situ* heating experiments on the spectral quality. Bearing this in mind, we aim to provide a guide to optimizing *in situ* heating experiments with respect to chemical EDXS analysis.

Introduction & Motivation

Energy-dispersive X-Ray spectroscopy (EDXS) is a straightforward and quick method for elemental characterization and mapping in transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Modern, fast devices for elemental characterization in TEM, such as silicon drift detector-based EDXS systems with large solid angles [1–4] in combination with high-brightness electron guns [5,6], allow for sensitive elemental characterization in *in situ* experiments. Here, temperature, electric fields or currents, gaseous or liquid flows [7,8], or stress and strain [9] can serve as external stimuli that initiate alterations in a sample. In heating experiments, the applicability of live analysis at elevated temperatures is inherently interesting for reversible processes, where one cannot “freeze” the state of a material to examine it at lower temperatures later [10,11]. Also, where recurring temperature cycles alter a sample substantially, or when the specimen evolution over time during (iso)thermal treatment is the focal point of interest, “true” *in situ* elemental characterization is a powerful tool. To gather proper results in EDXS,

however, one must cautiously regard the limits of a detector system when investigating samples at elevated temperatures [12]. Due to their band gap energies, semiconductor detectors are susceptible to infrared (IR) radiation. Emissions from a heater system add to the spectral input of a silicon-based detector system in a TEM as well.

In EDXS detectors - both in Si(Li) detectors [13] and in silicon drift detectors (SDD) [14] - the energy of a single incident X-ray creates many electron-hole-pairs, and an external bias collects the resulting charge. In addition, other photons may also contribute to a spectrum, if their energy is larger than the required energy for the excitation of an electron-hole pair (approx. 3.7 eV) [15]. At room temperature, this portion of low-energy photons is insignificant in comparison to generated X-rays. However, once an infrared emitter is present and heated to a few hundred degrees Celsius, the number of photons with enough energy to excite the detector grows to an extent, where this relation eventually inverts. The system is then busy counting infrared photons and as a result, dead time increases and X-ray detection efficiency drops.

Today, *in situ* TEM holder manufacturers mostly make use of micro-

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: robert.krisper@felmi-zfe.at (R. Krisper).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2021.113461>

Received 2 August 2021; Received in revised form 15 December 2021; Accepted 29 December 2021

Available online 31 December 2021

0304-3991/© 2022 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

electro-mechanical-system (MEMS) arrangements [12,16–19]. They produce novel devices for heating, applying an electrical bias or exposing a specimen to a gaseous atmosphere, or liquid flow. Such devices are often referred to as *heater chips*, *nano-heaters* or *nano-reactors* [17]. Furnace systems or other layouts [20,21] made simultaneous heating experiments and EDXS analysis cumbersome due to geometric constraints and comparably large heater structures. Nano-heaters (Fig. 1) come with low power consumption and thus lower IR emissions. Still, they do not automatically feature optimized geometries for EDXS measurements. Yet, EDXS systems are the kind of analytical detectors that mostly sit at low take-off angles due to geometric constraints inside a microscope. They thus require a large field of view to compensate for absorption. Dedicated *ex situ* holders, e.g. the Super-X holder by FEI, come with a special geometry to minimize absorption in the holder [22].

The influence of IR radiation and geometric relations on the detector performance have been addressed in the past [12,23], but to the best of the authors' knowledge, no in-depth analysis exists so far. We therefore systematically examine the influence of IR radiation on results and interpretation of EDX spectra through simulation and measurement. Topics of interest are the influence of holder geometry and tilting, incoming count rates and dead time of the detector system, noise, energy resolution and low Z limits for spectral identification. We provide a guideline on optimizing EDXS measurements while conducting heating experiments based on the sample holder geometry.

Instruments & Methods

Microscopes and sample holders

The microscopes and their corresponding EDXS systems used in this study are an FEI Titan³ G2 60 - 300 kV (S)TEM and an FEI TF20 (S)TEM. The Titan features a windowless Super-X system which comprises four silicon drift detectors (Q1 to Q4, 30 mm² each) [24], while the TF20 is equipped with an EDAX Si(Li) side-entry detector (ultra-thin polymer window).

To characterize the behaviour of EDXS detectors in *in situ* heating experiments, we used two sample holders manufactured by DENSolutions: a WildfireTM S3 single tilt (ST) sample holder and a WildfireTM D6 double tilt (DT) holder [25]. As shown in Fig. 2, they are different in how they hold a sample chip in place and thus exhibit substantially different shadowing behavior for various types of emitted radiation. The ST holder features a clamp to hold the chip in its bed and the contacting

Fig. 1. DENSolutions Wildfire nano-heater chip, resistively heated metallic spiral layer with a diameter of approx. 150 μm . Temperature-controlled via a four-point probe measurement; homogeneity across the active area surpasses 99.5%. Light microscopy image (Alicona Infinite Focus Microscope).

Fig. 2. Tips of holders for *in situ* heating experiments (DENSolutions). Top: ST holder (WildfireTM S3). Bottom: DT holder (WildfireTM D6), both for Thermo-Fisher Scientific electron microscopes. Note the cradle, holding the *nano heater* chip in the DT version, which effectively shadows a large portion of a low-take-off-angle detector system in default position, while the bed for a ST arrangement allows for a wide field of view.

needles sitting far from the actual heating spiral. In the DT holder, the chip is significantly smaller to allow for a reasonable beta tilting range without pole touches. All fixation parts of considerable size sit next to the central heating spiral. As seen in the photograph, the D6 nano-heater chip sits in a suspended cradle, which serves as mount but also introduces extensive shadowing of the EDXS detector.

Geometry and shadowing

The geometric relations between sample, sample holder and detector are important when optimising signal efficiency or determining relations needed for accurate elemental quantification results, e.g. the effective solid angle for the ζ -factor method [26,27]. For the Super-X detector each elevation angle is 18°, each detector tilt angle is 5° downwards, and the detectors are placed at a distance of 12.6 mm from the microscope's optical axis [24]. The time constant in the EDXS measurements presented here is 2.5 μs and the detectors are kept at -70 °C during operation.

Taking 3D models of the ST- and DT holders, we simulated the maximum possible detector collection solid angle with respect to tilting and x-y shift of the holder. Using Cinema 4D, we followed the procedure described by Kraxner *et al.* [28]. As illustrated in Fig. 3 (top), the ST holder allows for a maximum collection solid angle (full X-ray illumination) from -7° to +7° alpha tilt. Fig. 4 (top) furthermore shows that there is no possibility to shift the heated spiral out of the area where - at 0° tilt - shadowing is minimal. For the DT holder, however, the effective solid angle is low at any tilt angle due to the cradle and contacting needles. It is also very sensitive to the x-y shift of the holder (Figs. 3 and 4 (bottom)). Here, tilting towards two detectors maximizes the solid

Fig. 3. Simulated detector collection solid angle for X-rays with respect to tilting along the holder axis (α) towards or away from the four detectors Q1 to Q4 of a Super-X system. ST (top) and DT (bottom) sample holder. Most notably, the ST holder allows for a tilting of $\pm 7^\circ$ while retaining its maximum collection solid angle. Due to the cradle holding the nano-heater in position and other parts like the contacting needles, the shadowing is comparably large for the DT holder for a wide range of tilting angles.

angle and is therefore the preferred orientation for EDXS measurements.

Fig. 5 indicates how emission characteristics differ for X-rays generated in the sample and for infrared emission from a generic, $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$ large MEMS surface emitter [29] as used in infrared spectrometry. While the given shape of the infrared emission distribution is only representative for a spiral emitter shape of the chip shown in Fig. 1, we can easily identify the fundamental distinction from omnidirectional X-ray emissions. In an ideally flat sample bed, X-rays would fully illuminate the detector (green cone in Fig. 5, left), while only a small fraction of 2% to 20% of the maximum IR intensity actually reaches the detector. When, as explained above, geometries are not suitable for low-take-off-angle detectors, holder parts shadow some of the X-ray signal and the relative contribution of IR radiation increases (Fig. 5, center). In this case, tilting the sample holder towards the detector is a common approach. By doing so, however, we quickly find the detector exposed to much larger IR intensities (Fig. 5, right).

It is reasonable to assume that especially windowless detectors in EDXS systems will pick up infrared radiation emitted from any source, such as a MEMS emitter. To minimize this effect, placing a thin Al

Fig. 4. Simulated detector collection solid angle for X-rays with respect to shifting the holder in x and y direction (detector positions Q1 to Q4 indicated) of a Super-X system and a ST (top) and DT (bottom) holder at no tilt. The red circles indicate the active chip area (dashed for 2nd generation Wildfire chips with a smaller heating spiral). Again, the homogeneity in illumination is superior for the ST holder across all possible specimen positions along the heating spiral when compared with the DT version.

window in front of the detector certainly helps, but it also degrades light element detection efficiency. Exploiting the difference in spatial emission characteristics between X-rays and infrared radiation from a sample and its carrier could therefore prove a key factor in optimizing an experiment in terms of solid angle and detection efficiency for elemental analysis.

Infrared radiation counts and energy resolution

To our knowledge, the detection efficiency of X-ray detectors with respect to IR radiation that originates from a heated source inside the column has not been investigated in a TEM. In order to measure the detector's response to IR radiation only, one needs to eliminate any possible X-ray influence in the detector system produced by the electron beam. Therefore, we closed the column valves of the microscopes after positioning the centre of the heater chip's active area on the microscope optic axis and at the eucentric height. As a measure for the IR intensity, we used the count rate given by the detector software. We cross-checked the options to display the count rate and found the direct reading of the microscope controls to be most feasible for manually taking down the

Fig. 5. Schematics of emission characteristics for a MEMS heater (red) and X-rays (green) in polar patterns. We expect X-rays to emit uniformly in space, while the surface of a MEMS emitter will mainly emit in forward direction (a maximum of 100% in arbitrary units) and only a fraction of the maximum intensity to the side. Tilting a holder to avoid shadowing for X-rays from holder parts will ultimately lead to stronger IR irradiation exposure of the detector.

infrared-induced count rates presented in this work. Opening the detector shutter would then result in the number of events per second induced by electronic noise, thermal fluctuations and actual thermal infrared radiation.

To characterize pure IR emissions, we used 1st (type XT) and 2nd generation (type GT) MEMS heaters by DENSolutions that either come in a through-hole configuration for lamella samples or with an electron-transparent SiN_x membrane of 20 nm to 30 nm thickness for particle deposition. The membrane chips were coated on the bottom side with an approximately 10 nm thin AuPd layer (80% Au, 20% Pd sputter target). In-house, we used a Leica sputter coater (EM ACE 600) for the 1st generation chips, while DENSolutions coated the 2nd generation chips (SC7620 Mini Sputter Coater/Glow Discharge System). Apart from evaluating the IR emissions of a chip that carries an actual sample, AuPd on SiN_x is a convenient system for analysis of the signal-to-background ratio at the nitrogen K line. It also allows us to compare the energy resolution from element peaks in the low energy range (Si-K, Au-M, Pd-L) to the lines in a higher energy region (Au-L).

Measurements & Results

In this section, we present the influence of infrared radiation in the detector system by recording IR intensities as a function of the set sample temperature and with respect to the holder tilt. In doing so for each of the two microscope-detector combinations, we aim to provide temperature limits below which an operator would still be able to retrieve reliable EDXS data from the respective system.

Infrared induced counts in temperature series

To mimic conditions with minimal shadowing, we tilted the DT holder 25° towards two detectors of the Super-X system (see Fig. 4) when picking up the pure infrared signal over a range of temperatures. An alpha tilt of -25° corresponds to tilting towards Q3 and Q4, which sit across the holder axis vis-à-vis to Q2 and Q1, respectively (see Fig. 6). Although not necessary in a regular experiment, we also tilted the ST holder for the same angle to ensure that emission characteristics of the heater chips would not intrinsically alter the results.

Fig. 6 illustrates the acquired IR signal for different configurations of holder (chip) and sample. For reasons explained below, we display the measured data series in two ways: we plot the IR intensity with respect to the temperature, whereas we also show the same data as an Arrhenius plot with IR intensity plotted logarithmically against 1/T.

Fig. 6. Detected infrared emissions from different heating chips at a tilt of 25° towards detectors (1st chip generation, Titan, Super-X, detectors Q3 and Q4) and temperature set points from 480 °C to 600 °C. Forward emissions increase greatly for the cradle-embedded DT chips when sputter-coated with AuPd as a sample system.

As one can see from Fig. 6, the infrared-generated signal does not exceed regular detector noise in the Titan³ G2 with a Super-X up to 480 °C. In the displayed temperature range, dead times are less than 10% for temperatures up to 600 °C.

With the large shadowing of the DT holder cradle, infrared emissions are surprisingly about one order of magnitude higher with an AuPd sputter layer than without one. As the layer is adherent to the bottom of the chip, this should not stem from an altered surface emission coefficient in comparison to the uncoated through-hole configuration. However, whereas this finding applies to the DT holder, it does not for the ST version. We therefore deduce that the cradle of the DT holder must be IR reflective and – supported by Figs. 8 and 9 – acts as a mirror: it directs large portions of the otherwise “lost” IR emissions towards the detectors.

In the current (second) heater chip generation, the smaller heated area and the lower overall power consumption reduce the IR emission (Fig. 7). The difference in forward emission between through-hole or blank variants of the first and latest chips has increased drastically, allowing for measurements of the same quality up to 680 °C with the latter. We found the dead time of the system to be at 40% when reaching 750 °C; for the Super-X system, recordings of spectra begin to suffer in quality at about $5 \cdot 10^4$ cps per detector. Note that net count rates deviated between detectors for infrared counts despite the geometrical symmetry, while they would count roughly the same number of X-rays

Fig. 7. Detected infrared emissions from heating chips at a holder tilt of 25° towards detectors (Titan, Super-X, detectors Q1 and Q2), comparing 1st and 2nd generation of Wildfire™ heater chips. When blank (i.e. in through-hole configuration), the second chip generation exhibits lower forward emissions than the first chip generation.

(calibrated detector).

For the conventional, LN₂-cooled Si(Li) side-entry detector on our TF20 200 kV (S)TEM relatively high dead times occur at any temperatures of the sample beyond 400 °C (e.g. > 60% for 480 °C) with time constants between 10 μs and 100 μs. This difference compared to the measurements on the Super-X system arises from the fact that, due to their lower capacitance, SDDs can handle much higher count rates compared to Si(Li) detectors [30]. The system initiates an emergency detector retraction at a threshold of $5 \cdot 10^4$ counts per second. It seems noteworthy that only incoming radiation which excites the detector above a set cut-off energy contributes to the values shown in Fig. 8.

We performed the measurement on infrared induced counts inside the TF20 at an alpha tilt of 30° towards the detector. Here, emissions from the ST holder result in much larger count rates compared to the DT variant. With the time constant of 50 μs (used throughout the Si(Li) measurements), at 580 °C, the dead time is almost at 100% for all but the DT holder with through-hole heater chips.

For both SDD and Si(Li) detector systems, above 480 °C infrared radiation contributes increasingly to the spectrum background signal. The windowless Super-X system can still handle these count rates up to 600 °C and 680 °C for different holder-chip-sample-configurations. The increased dead times are induced by excessive count rates. They impede

Fig. 8. Detected infrared emissions from heating chips at a holder tilt of 30° towards the detector (TF20, EDAX side-entry EDXS detector). Here the holder tilt leads to substantial shadowing in the DT system, which is why the detected intensity for the ST system is higher. The substantial difference between forward emissions for the sputtered AuPd-configuration in the DT holder prevails. Above 580 °C, the dead time is close to 100% and a “saturation” effect occurs.

the recording of events with the Si(Li) system in that temperature range substantially when keeping the sample holder under an angle that is usually used for maximising X-ray counts.

In all of the temperature series above, the measured quantity is proportional to the number of photons with sufficient energy E_{min} to create electron-hole pairs and consequently a detector response. E_{min} determines the slope and hence is similar for a Si(Li) detector and SDD (see supplementary information). Indeed, the comparison of data sets shown in Fig. 9 supports this idea: we find values for E_{min} of approximately 3.7 eV for the Si(Li) and 3.2 eV for the SDD respectively.

Infrared induced counts in tilt series

Through recording tilt series at 600 °C sample temperature, we compared the measurements for IR induced counts (Fig. 10) to our predictions for X-ray shadowing from simulations (Fig. 3) with the Titan and Super-X system. The relations for IR emissions from through-hole and AuPd configurations persist roughly. When tilting towards two detectors and especially the shadowing of the DT holder decreases gradually.

The directed emissions within the take-off angle comprising detector elevation (18°) and alpha tilt (0° to 26°, absolute value) grow linearly for both, ST- and DT holder. As shown in Fig. 4, the combined shadowing for detectors Q3 and Q4 is low with the ST holder, but large with the DT holder. However, those simulations are only valid for X-rays: for infrared radiation, reflections from the cradle and surrounding parts, as well as the emission characteristics of the chip determine the number of counts with progressing tilt angle. Downward IR emissions from the chip can have a significant impact when they are reflected by the lower pole piece and collected by the detector. However, due to the narrow pole piece gap, this IR signal source does not appear dominant in our experimental setups.

For the TF20 and its side-entry Si(Li) detector, we did not simulate

Fig. 10. Detected IR emissions with respect to tilt towards detectors Q3 and Q4 of the Super-X system at T = 600 °C.

the X-ray shadowing. Still, as shown in Fig. 11, tilt series at a fixed temperature provide some insight and results for both holders, which diverge substantially due to shadowing and reflections from contacting needles and holder cradle. The angle at which detection of infrared radiation reaches its maximum lies between 22° and 24° for the ST holder. Here, count rates from the IR signal at 600 °C exceeded the maximum system count rate (50000 cps) and would result in automatic detector retraction. Again, relations between through-hole and AuPd configurations are in rough accordance with the results from temperature series (Fig. 8). For the ST holder, the larger angle dependence of IR induced

Fig. 9. Comparison of Arrhenius-plot data sets from Figs. 6 to 8 for temperature series across ST and DT holders, 1st and 2nd generation chips (where available), in through-hole configuration and with an AuPd sputter layer at the TF20 and Titan.

Fig. 11. Detected IR emissions with respect to tilt towards a side entry detector in the TF20 at $T = 600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The shadowing stemming from holder parts and contact needles is evident for the DT holder.

counts points towards an increase in directed forward emission by the AuPd layer. We can also attribute local minima in the tilt series for the DT holder to shadowing and reflections from the holder cradle and the contacting needles.

Keeping the ST holder at a relatively flat angle is feasible for X-ray shadowing and avoiding infrared radiation induced counts. For the DT holder, we found the situation to be much more challenging. Tilting the holder towards the detector yields larger X-ray count numbers and lower X-ray signals from other sample or holder parts. Unfortunately, the detector sits at an elevation, where the contacting needles of the holder will still be directly in the line of sight to the sample (compare Fig. 2). Said detector system is then also more prone to strong infrared emissions in forward direction and for IR reflections.

Spectra

While we have addressed the occurrence of counting events induced by infrared radiation, we have yet to look at the effects of a massive low-energy signal pickup. Furthermore, we may possibly need to bear in

mind the effects of unusually high dead times when acquiring actual X-ray spectra. As mentioned above, an AuPd layer on the SiN_x membrane provides a sufficient variety of peaks across a broad energy range. At the low spectral end, the N-K line serves as an indicator whether or not one is still able to discern low Z elements from a background. The distant Au-L peak adds information on an energy dependent deviation in relative and absolute energy resolution decrease at increased temperatures or count rates.

With the Super-X system, peaks are sharp and clear even with the first-generation heater chip design between room temperature and $600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Fig. 12 illustrates the low-energy end of the spectra. Besides the peak broadening (decrease in energy resolution) and the drastic reduction of residual carbon (282 eV) at elevated temperatures, the zero-energy noise peak broadens so that a large flank appears beyond the cut-off energy at 100 eV. It stems from IR radiation and contributes substantially to the local background at energies of low-Z elements. This may complicate peak integration for N-K and its surrounding neighbors, when performing an automated quantification. The overall count rate at $600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was larger than $2.5 \cdot 10^4$ cps, with only about 10 % of the counts stemming from X-ray signals (compare Fig. 10).

With the Si(Li) system featuring an ultrathin polymer window, we find spectra to deteriorate visibly during the heating experiment. As shown in Fig. 13, the noise peak contributes to the spectra above the cut-off energy (70 eV) up to 250 eV, suggesting a temperature limit of $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. At $580\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, we found no distinct N-K peak due to a substantial background signal and overall noise in the spectrum. Measurements at $600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ already triggered the automated high-count retraction of the side-entry detector, so that an acquisition of spectra was not possible. Here, noise and background signal from a low-energy peak, which spreads beyond the cut-off energy, significantly grow above $560\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. They render the detection of low Z elements (like N, O) impossible from $580\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ onwards.

Energy resolution

Comparing the FWHM of characteristic peaks, we find a steady broadening with increasing IR emissions caused by elevated sample heater temperatures. Obviously, holder tilt and setups that lead to higher infrared count rates cause a larger decay in spectral quality than those, where the directed IR emission does not irradiate the EDXS detectors. For reasons of convention (see supplementary information), Fig. 14 compares the interpolated energy resolution values of Mn- K_{α} for representative experimental setups: An un-tilted ST holder and a tilted DT holder with the same heater chip generation, as well as an un-tilted

Fig. 12. Spectra recorded from a 20 nm thick AuPd sputter sample on SiN_x (ST holder, 1st generation heater chips, 0° tilt) with a Super-X detector at specimen temperatures up to $600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 13. Spectra recorded from a 20 nm thick AuPd sputter sample on SiN_x (ST holder, 1st generation heater chips, 30° tilt towards detector) with an Si(Li) detector at specimen temperatures up to 580 °C.

Fig. 14. Energy resolution at E_{Mn-K α} for the ST holder (1st & 2nd generation heater chips, 0° tilt), DT holder (1st generation heater chips, 25° tilt towards detectors) and ST holder (2nd generation heater chips, 25° tilt towards detectors) with the Super-X detector at specimen temperatures up to 600 °C.

ST holder with the improved 2nd generation heater chip design. With the 1st generation ST holder kept at 0° tilt, the FWHM of Mn-K α increases by more than 25 eV at 600 °C, and by more than 40 eV for the tilted DT holder. In comparison, the 2nd heater chip generation is a major improvement; yet still 15 eV are lost in resolution at 600 °C. For reference purposes, Fig. 14 also includes data for a tilted, 2nd generation ST heater, further underlining the importance of the holder orientation when trying to minimize IR impact on X-ray spectra.

We want to mention that degradation in energy resolution for high count rates has been described previously [31], but that the peak broadening caused by IR radiation exceeds those values by far. As shown above, the detector system electronics that have to process those low-energy events play a crucial role in the retrieval of high-quality spectra at elevated sample temperatures. Most interestingly, the loss in energy resolution (in eV) is larger for lower energies, which renders the detection of light elements through EDXS at high IR irradiation cumbersome or impossible (see supplementary information for details). A system that is not specifically trimmed to such needs will therefore most likely provide poor performance for EDXS at elevated

temperatures.

Summary and practical considerations

In this work, we determined the influence of IR radiation, emitted from state-of-the-art sample heaters for in situ TEM analysis, on EDXS detector systems. To do so, we compared a WildfireTM S3 single tilt (ST) holder and a WildfireTM D6 double tilt (DT) holder by DENSolutions. We recorded IR induced counts across various temperatures as well as holder tilt series to evaluate emission characteristics and angles for two different detector systems: a Super-X multi-detector system and a Si(Li) side-entry detector.

Simulations for the Super-X detector system revealed the optimum tilting angles for X-ray detector collection solid angle to lie between -7° and +7° alpha tilt for the ST holder. They also suggested maximizing the tilt for the DT holder. Tilt series with the heated chip, however, showed that tilting towards detectors strongly increases the amount of infrared radiation on the detector. While the used ST holder would allow for efficient measurements under low take-off angles, the DT holder – due to its construction – did not. Ultimately, finding a trade-off between effective solid angle and infrared-induced counts a detector system can handle is necessary, which is much easier for holders with low shadowing, such as the used ST holder.

In heat series, the increase in picked up IR signal matches theoretical considerations and when displaying them in Arrhenius plots, we find reasonable results: our measured values of around 3.5 eV correspond well with the nominal value of 3.8 eV for the average photon energy needed to create charge carriers in silicon-based detectors.

With the windowless Super-X SDD system at the FEI Titan, for nanoparticles and FIB lamellae, we found that the detector could conveniently handle the infrared emissions from blank chips for measurements up to 750 °C. Experiments on infrared-reflective film specimen worked up to 650 °C with the latest heater chip generation. The actual spectra, however, change before reaching those points. For Mn-K α we observed a peak broadening of about 15 eV between 480 °C and 600 °C in the optimum orientation with the ST holder and 2nd generation heater chips. It is more than 40 eV for the DT holder, when tilted towards detectors. Especially the detection sensitivity for light elements in the low energy portion of spectra suffered from the degradation in energy resolution and a larger background signal.

For the Si(Li) detector, the signal-to-background ratio drops notably already at 500 °C. When taking the sample to 580 °C, low energy peaks become completely indiscernible from the background while count rates

and dead times increase rapidly. Note that these measurements have been conducted using the ST holder which is significantly better suited for EDXS analysis than the DT holder.

Quite naturally, different holders, chips and detector types all contribute to the results of an optimized heating experiment. For heating experiments, recording tilt series makes sense at a fixed temperature that would yield infrared-induced counts, even with substantial holder shadowing present, to identify IR reflections from surrounding parts. At the same time, we do not want to overexpose and thus shut off the detector at the “optimum” incident angle.

Depending on count rates a detector system can handle, there is an optimal tilting angle for doing EDX spectroscopy in every system for elevated sample temperatures. It is easily accessible by following the routines presented in this work through closing the column valves and tracking the count rate at elevated sample temperature across a tilt series. Complementary to these results, shadowing simulations aid in finding an optimum balance between infrared emission exposition and detector collection solid angle for X-rays. Consequently, sacrificing a portion of the solid angle for spectral quality may be feasible.

While the results presented in this work are explicitly valid for specific holder-detector combinations, the general findings also apply to other MEMS-based heating setups and EDXS systems. We also want to keep in mind that practical limits are sometimes situational and may vary greatly, depending on the composition of a sample and implicitly necessary energy-dependent energy resolution. Of course, detector type, arrangement and processing electronics must also provide a sufficient performance. Moreover, we need to bear in mind what types of holders are primarily intended for use in analytics and which are not – and how those can be improved to meet demands.

Funding sources

This work was supported by the Austrian Cooperative Research Facility, the Austrian Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology (BMK) and the European Union Horizon 2020 programmes ESTEEM2 (grant No. 312483) and ESTEEM3 (grant No. 823717).

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Yevheniy Pivak is an employee of DENSSolutions; they developed and are marketing the Wildfire S3 and Wildfire D6 sample holders and the corresponding heater chips used in this work. The other authors declare no competing interests.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge Marina Zakhovska for sharing her knowledge on the described holder systems. JL thanks Johanna Kraxner for fruitful discussions on simulations with Cinema 4D.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.ultramic.2021.113461.

References

- [1] M. Watanabe, D.W. Ackland, D.B. Williams, The effect of large solid angles of collection on quantitative X-ray microanalysis in the AEM, *J. Microsc.* 195 (1999) 34–43, <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2818.1999.00481.x>.

- [2] N.J. Zaluzec, Innovative Instrumentation for Analysis of Nanoparticles: The π Steradian Detector, *Microsc. Today* 17 (2009) 56–59, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1551929509000224>.
- [3] J.S. Iwanczyk, B.E. Patt, C.R. Tull, J.D. Segal, C.J. Kenney, J. Bradley, B. Hedman, K.O. Hodgson, Large area silicon drift detectors for X-rays-new results, *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.* 46 (1999) 284–288, <https://doi.org/10.1109/23.775529>.
- [4] P. Schlossmacher, D.O. Klenov, B. Freitag, H.S. von Harrach, Enhanced Detection Sensitivity with a New Windowless XEDS System for AEM Based on Silicon Drift Detector Technology, *Microsc. Today* 18 (2010) 14–20, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1551929510000404>.
- [5] B. Freitag, G. Knippels, S. Kujawa, M. van der Stam, D. Hubert, P.C. Tiemeijer, C. Kisielowski, P. Denes, A. Minor, U. Dahmen, First performance measurements and application results of a new high brightness Schottky field emitter for HR-S/TEM at 80–300kV acceleration voltage, *Microsc Microanal* 14 (2008) 1370–1371, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1431927608087370>.
- [6] FEI Company, Titan™ G2 with ChemiSTEM™ Technology, A revolution in atomic analytics, Application note, 2010.
- [7] H.H. Pérez Garza, K. Zuo, Y. Pivak, D. Morsink, M. Zakhovska, M. Pen, S. van Weperen, Q. Xu, MEMS-based system for in-situ biasing and heating solutions inside the TEM, in: *European Microscopy Congress 2016, Proceedings*, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim, Germany, 2016, pp. 237–238.
- [8] J.F. Creemer, S. Helveg, G.H. Hovelting, S. Ullmann, P.J. Kooyman, A. M. Molenbroek, H.W. Zandbergen, P.M. Sarro, MEMS Nanoreactor for Atomic-Resolution Microscopy of Nanomaterials in their Working State, in: *2009 IEEE 22nd International Conference on Micro Electro Mechanical Systems 1*, IEEE, Sorrento, Italy, 2009, pp. 76–79.
- [9] Y. Zhu, H.D. Espinosa, An electromechanical material testing system for in situ electron microscopy and applications, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 102 (2005) 14503–14508, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0506544102>.
- [10] Y. Li, L. Zang, D.L. Jacobs, J. Zhao, X. Yue, C. Wang, In situ study on atomic mechanism of melting and freezing of single bismuth nanoparticles, *Nat. Commun.* 8 (2017) 14462, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14462>.
- [11] A. Schilling, B. Barton, J.R. Jinschek, L. Mele, P. Dona, J. Ringnald, M. Arredondo, J.F. Einsle, M. Gregg, Live Imaging of Reversible Domain Evolution in BaTiO₃ on the Nanometer Scale Using in-situ STEM and TEM, *Microsc Microanal* 20 (2014) 1560–1561, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1431927614009532>.
- [12] L. Mele, S. Konings, P. Dona, F. Evertz, C. Mitterbauer, P. Faber, R. Schampers, J. R. Jinschek, A MEMS-based heating holder for the direct imaging of simultaneous in-situ heating and biasing experiments in scanning/transmission electron microscopes, *Microsc. Res. Tech.* 79 (2016) 239–250, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jemt.22623>.
- [13] J.W. Mayer, The “State-of-The Art” in Nuclear Particle Detectors, *IRE Trans. on Nuclear Science* 9 (1962) 124–134, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNS.1962.4315985>.
- [14] E. Gatti, P. Rehak, Semiconductor drift chamber — An application of a novel charge transport scheme, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research* 225 (1984) 608–614, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-5087\(84\)90113-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-5087(84)90113-3).
- [15] C.E. Lyman, D.B. Williams, J.I. Goldstein, X-ray detectors and spectrometers, *Ultramicroscopy* 28 (1989) 137–149, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3991\(89\)90286-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3991(89)90286-6).
- [16] J. Damiano, D.P. Nackashi, S.E. Mick, A MEMS-based Technology Platform for in-situ TEM Heating Studies, *Microsc Microanal* 14 (2008) 1332–1333, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1431927608088363>.
- [17] L. Mele, F. Santagata, E. Iervolino, M. Mihailovic, T. Rossi, A.T. Tran, H. Schellevis, J.F. Creemer, P.M. Sarro, A molybdenum MEMS microhotplate for high-temperature operation, *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical* 188 (2012) 173–180, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sna.2011.11.023>.
- [18] Hummingbird Scientific, Product Series 1550 In-situ TEM Biasing and Heating Holder, Product Brochure (2014).
- [19] Mel-Build Corporation, TEM Specimen Holder and Stage Solution, Product Brochure 006 (2021).
- [20] Inc. Gatan, Single Tilt Heating Holder, Model, Datasheet 628 (2018).
- [21] T. Kamino, H. Saka, HREM In-Situ Experiment at Very High Temperatures, in: P. L. Gai (Ed.), *In-Situ Microscopy in Materials Research*, Springer US, Boston, MA, 1997, pp. 173–199.
- [22] W. Xu, J.H. Dycus, X. Sang, J.M. LeBeau, A numerical model for multiple detector energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy in the transmission electron microscope, *Ultramicroscopy* 164 (2016) 51–61, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2016.02.004>.
- [23] N.J. Zaluzec, A. Janssen, M.G. Burke, D. Gardiner, S. Walden, Modifications to Membrane Heater Holders to Enable XEDS in the AEM, *Microsc Microanal* 21 (2015) 961–962, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1431927615005607>.
- [24] H.S. von Harrach, P. Dona, B. Freitag, H. Soltan, A. Niculae, M. Rohde, An integrated multiple silicon drift detector system for transmission electron microscopes, *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 241 (2010) 12015, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/241/1/012015>.
- [25] B.V. DENSSolutions, Wildfire In Situ Heating Systems For TEM platforms, Product Brochure (2015).
- [26] N.J. Zaluzec, Analytical formulae for calculation of X-ray detector solid angles in the scanning and scanning/transmission analytical electron microscope, *Microsc. Microanal.* 20 (2014) 1318–1326, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1431927614000956>.

- [27] M. Watanabe, D.B. Williams, The quantitative analysis of thin specimens: a review of progress from the Cliff-Lorimer to the new zeta-factor methods, *J. Microsc.* 221 (2006) 89–109, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2818.2006.01549.x>.
- [28] J. Kraxner, M. Schäfer, O. Röschel, G. Kothleitner, G. Haberfehlner, M. Paller, W. Grogger, Quantitative EDXS: Influence of geometry on a four detector system, *Ultramicroscopy* 172 (2017) 30–39, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2016.10.005>.
- [29] S. Weise, B. Steinbach, S. Biermann, MEMS-based IR-sources. *Silicon Photonics XI*, SPIE, San Francisco, California, United States, 2016, p. 97521E.
- [30] D.B. Williams, C.B. Carter, *Transmission electron microscopy: A textbook for materials science*, Springer, New York, London, 2009 second ed.
- [31] D.E. Newbury, N.W.M. Ritchie, Performing elemental microanalysis with high accuracy and high precision by scanning electron microscopy/silicon drift detector energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometry (SEM/SDD-EDS), *J. Mater. Sci.* 50 (2015) 493–518, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-014-8685-2>.